

Table 2. Grain yield of CR1018 as influenced by transplanting date, seedling age, and spacing. Cuttack, India, 1984 wet season.

Spacing (cm)	Seedling age (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean yield (t/ha)
		15 Jul	15 Aug	15 Sep	
15 × 15	30	5.5	4.9	2.8	4.4
	60	3.9	4.0	3.4	3.8
20 × 15	30	5.2	3.5	2.7	3.8
	60	5.5	4.1	3.3	4.3
20 × 20	30	5.3	4.0	2.6	4.0
	60	5.2	3.9	3.2	4.1
25 × 20	30	5.4	3.9	2.2	3.8
	60	5.3	3.8	2.9	4.0
Mean		5.2	4.0	2.9	
LSD (0.05)	main plot (planting dates)	=		1.0	
LSD (0.05)	subplot (spacing × seedling age)	=		ns	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing planting dates (spacing × seedling age)	=		1.1	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing (spacing × seedling age) within a planting date	=		0.8	

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Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of BR3 rice to duckweed (*Lemna minor*) application

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Duckweed is a minute, diploid spore-producing, vascular, free-floating aquatic plant that contains around 4% N. It grows abundantly in stagnant

water in Bangladesh, especially during the monsoon. We studied its use as an organic N source for rice.

Duckweed was grown in earthen pots 56.41 cm in diameter (1 m²), filled with 60 kg air-dried soil and 72 liters of water. Composition (oven-dried basis) of the duckweed was 4.2% N; 2.3% P; 3.02% K; and 29.64% organic C.

Two seedlings of rice variety BR3 were planted in pots containing 10 kg soil and fertilized with 35 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Soil was silty loam with pH 5.2, 0.84% organic C, 80 kg 2M KCl

extractable N/ha, 18.4 kg Olsen's reagent extractable P/ha, and 134 kg neutral N ammonium acetate extractable K/ha.

Treatments were 5 t fresh duckweed/ha = 833 kg oven-dried duckweed/ha, and 5.0, 2.5, 1.9, and 1.43 t oven-dried duckweed/ha and 2 combinations of oven-dried duckweed + urea. Each treatment was replicated three times in a completely randomized design.

Incorporating 5 t oven-dried duckweed/ha increased grain yields 52% and straw yields 50% (see table). Combined 20 kg urea N/ha + 1.43 t duckweed/ha increased grain yields 62% and straw yields 67%. Urea applied at 80 kg N/ha increased grain yields 50% and straw yields 44%. Oven-dried duckweed at 5 t/ha was better than urea at 80 kg N/ha.

N uptake was greater in the treatments where urea was applied. □

Yield of and N uptake by BR3 rice as affected by application of duckweed and urea.

t/ha	Duckweed applied		Urea applied (kg N/ha)	Yield (g/pot)		N uptake (mg/pot)
	kg N/ha	As % weight of 10 kg soil		Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	0	8.51	7.21	140.4
5.00 ^a	35	0.250	0	9.80	7.31	165.1
5.00	210	0.250	0	13.00	10.82	279.4
2.50	105	0.125	0	12.01	8.55	235.9
1.90	80	0.095	0	12.40	10.00	251.1
1.43	60	0.070	0	11.94	9.77	225.6
1.43	60	0.070	20	13.80	12.11	318.3
0.95	40	0.048	40	13.50	11.28	313.1
0.00	0	0.000	80	12.80	10.42	327.8
LSD (P=0.01)				2.36	1.11	

^aFresh duckweed incorporated 7 d before transplanting.

Using iron pyrite to increase nitrogen efficiency in rice under sodic conditions

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N efficiency in rice under sodic conditions is reduced because of heavy

gaseous N losses through volatilization and denitrification. We experimented with 3 levels of pyrite (0, 40%, and 60% of gypsum requirement [GR]) and N (40, 80, and 120 kg/ha) in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

The sodic soil had pH 9.2, E_{Ce} 7.2 dS/m, ESP 38, hydraulic conductivity 0.18 cm/h, and sandy loam texture. Pyrite containing 22% sulfur was mixed into the top 10-cm soil. Moisture was maintained between field capacity and saturation for 1 wk before transplanting to enhance oxidation. Jaya rice seedlings 40-d-old were planted at 4-5/hill in unpuddled soil. The crop was raised with ponded water following recommended agronomic practices. N was applied in 3 splits; half before

Effect of iron pyrites on grain yield of rice, and uptake and percent recovery of applied N at 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha. ^aFaizabad, India.

Pyrite (%) of GR	N uptake (kg/ha)			Grain yield (t/ha)			Change in soil pH (1:2:5)
	40	80	120	40	80	120	
No pyrite	4.9 (5.5)	7.2 (5.6)	8.2 (4.6)	1.22 (-)	1.61 (-)	1.85 (-)	9.2
40	7.4 (11.8)	10.4 (9.6)	14.0 (9.4)	2.10 (74.5)	2.75 (70.8)	3.00 (67.6)	8.6
60	8.8 (15.3)	13.6 (13.6)	16.2 (11.3)	2.66 (118.0)	3.56 (121.0)	3.86 (108.6)	8.3

^aN uptake in control = 2.7 kg/ha. Grain yield in control = 0.8 t/ha. Values in parentheses indicate percent recovery of applied N and percent response to N with pyrites, respectively.

transplanting, 1/4 one mo after transplanting, and 1/4 at panicle initiation.

Pyrite increased recovery of applied N

(see table). Maximum N recovery was with 60% GR and 40 kg N/ha. Grain yield also increased with pyrite application. □

Disease management

Effect of micronutrient on rice brown spot (BS) incidence

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BS caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* can cause up to 20% yield losses in tropical rice. The disease occurs mostly after late tillering, when micronutrients are needed for the reproductive phase. We studied the influence of soil and foliar applications of micronutrients on BS incidence during 1985-86 and 1986-87, using IR20 as test variety.

The micronutrients were applied as foliar sprays, on the soil, or as both soil and foliar sprays (see table). Soil application was done before transplanting; leaves were sprayed 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). Natural incidence of BS was recorded on 20 leaves/plot at the dough stage and the disease index calculated by McKinney's formula.

BS incidence was lowest with soil application of 25 kg FeSO₄/ha + 0.5% foliar spray 30 and 50 DT, or with soil

BS incidence at different levels of micronutrients. ^a Madurai, India, 1985-87.

Micronutrient	Treatment		Percentage disease index	
	Application	Dosage	1985-86	1986-87
CuSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	20.9 (27.20)	18.4 (25.40)
ZnSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.0 (29.33)	18.1 (25.18)
MnSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	19.6 (26.27)	19.1 (25.92)
MgSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.1 (29.40)	22.1 (28.04)
FeSO ₄	Foliar spray	0.5%	24.9 (29.93)	18.0 (25.10)
ZnSO ₄	To soil	20 kg/ha	21.4 (27.56)	21.2 (27.42)
FeSO ₄	To soil	25 kg/ha	25.2 (30.13)	26.2 (30.79)
MnSO ₄	To soil	25 kg/ha	25.0 (30.00)	25.6 (30.40)
CuSO ₄	To soil	1 kg/ha	20.00 (26.56)	22.2 (28.11)
CaSO ₄	To soil	500 kg/ha	23.7 (29.13)	30.4 (33.46)
CuSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	1 kg/ha + 0.5%	16.1 (23.66)	15.5 (23.19)
ZnSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	20 kg/ha + 0.5%	32.7 (34.88)	17.9 (25.03)
MnSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	25 kg/ha + 0.5%	20.4 (26.85)	22.6 (28.38)
FeSO ₄	To soil + foliar spray	25 kg/ha + 0.5%	16.7 (24.12)	14.9 (22.79)
Control		—	40.6 (39.58)	35.6 (36.63)
LSD (P=0.05)			(2.156)	(2.222)

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed values.